

THE ROLE OF TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract:

This article highlights the convenience and benefits of information technology in teaching foreign languages.

Key words: method, methodological system, internet, culture, innovative technologies, authentic learning environment, autonomy, ICT, Internet educational resources, ELT.

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In recent years, the use of information and communication technologies in the field of education has become the most important issue. This means not only new technical devices but also new reforms, changes and a new renaissance in education. It shows to students the role of information technologies in education, communication culture, and new ways of working with this type of technical tools in practical lessons.[1] I think to carry out these reforms in practice, firstly the government must be developed economically in high rate, and these experiments must be tried before in the educational infrastructure.

According to the scientific research of national and international scientists, there are 2 main meanings of the word “method”:

- achieving the intended goal is the key to success;
- complete methodological system and a specific direction of the educational process used in different periods for the prospective development of science. [2].

By the 21st century, the use of the Internet in teaching foreign languages is becoming more popular.[3] I agree with this idea because it also develops a culture of internet usage among language learners along with foreign language teaching. Technology offers foreign language teachers a chance to supplement their instruction by: Making learning visible: Technology can bring another culture into the classroom. Using technology tools that connect to foreign lands and display how others live allows students to see and experience language in a whole new way. Last years learning English meant just handouts, writing essays and working on mistakes, books, assignments and assessments. In short, it was considered that education and learning of foreign languages could not be imagined without a teacher, without a book, without a blackboard. In today's fast-paced world, learning foreign languages has acquired a new meaning. Innovative technologies have become an integral part of language classrooms, teachers use videos, audio podcasts, electronic dictionaries to explain foreign languages to students in a new way, that is, topics and materials. Through these technologies, students learn foreign languages quickly and efficiently. [4]

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The usage of innovative technologies in the teaching of foreign languages gives a special spirit to the teaching process. Each lesson will have effective discussion if the language learners have some knowledge of the topic and if the teacher's presentation based on innovative technologies. For instance: "Round-table" is one of the kind of technique in foreign language. This activity helps language learners to develop their speaking skills. 10-15 students sit around one table and discuss a specific problem. A host has an important role during the activity; it can be student or a teacher. The goal of this activity is not to solve the issue but to discuss the problem and collect as much information as possible, when students sit around a table, they have eye contact with other discussion participants, everyone feels involved and equally important. "Round-table" activity is related to "a role play" or "business play". [5] Information technology will certainly help us in the implementation of these activities, because it is appropriate to play various interactive games, to show videos or films, so that students do not get bored during the language learning process.

Students always have positive attitude to Information and Communication Technologies toward the language education and learning. Because learners seemed that are more succeeded in lessons and more encourages to learn by themselves. By this they have improved self-confidence and enjoyment while they are utilizing computer-based resources.

Another significance is that students own an opportunity to take knowledge on aspects of language which they want to focus on learning strategies also they are able to learn free without any sense of fear from the other co-learners, therefore autonomy is supported by certain modern gadgets and services provided by Information technologies whilst ordinary traditional teaching style failed to present that opportunity which was given by online basis. Language learners feel themselves free in authentic environment, reason why learner can go with another people from overseas across some continents to sense real impression with native speakers that contributes them effectively to some extent.

Likewise, as a teacher this method namely IT can assist for them to conduct lessons properly and active, also there are an access to provide several high-quality details, materials, online quiz tests, productive exercises with relying on modern technologies. This can save their academic time to another beneficial stuffs like self-evaluation or personal life. Despite these available chances, teachers should be well-educated in terms of managing these facilities in order to keep their own positions. [6]

Basic materials on the Internet contain items in text, auditory, vision on various topics to grow the number of possibilities. In turn, students have to make productive use of details provided by IT to satisfy educational and professional interest and needs. Language researches point out 5 types of Internet educational resources:

1. Hotlist. This is a list of educative sites which are selected the best ones to various studied topic. It would take less time to find required information out of websites because of this method. One thing is that to find some data you want can be entering some keywords to search button.

2. Treasure hunt. This way resembles the Hotlist and Multimedia scrapbook. It usually includes links with various Edu-sites on certain topic. The basic difference is that each link reviews some questions on the content of that website. At the end of the approach students may be requested one more general question about overview of topic.

3. Subject sampler. A Subject sampler supplies different links with links from textual and multimedia materials. After gained such aspect of theme students have to perform replies to given questions. This is targeted that to debate unsolvable and global problems also they must reveal their own opinions

4. Multimedia scrapbook. A Multimedia scrapbook is a store of different multimedia resources. In this provides a number of links not only with textual sites, but also the photos, music, video clips, graphic information, up-to-date 3D projects.

5. WebQuest. WebQuest is an inquiry-oriented lesson formation in which most or all the data students work with comes from the web. These can be made using various programs, including a simple word processing document that contains links to websites. [7]

It must be said that most vital urgent for university entrance and organizing well-paid recruits in the commercial sector. According to recent statistics new English learners are expanding day by day in Uzbekistan, in order to grant them with proper teaching methods, our education system supplied modern computers and good connection system to enhance effectiveness of the teaching process. Therefore, these goods include multimedia in ELT to become more English contexts, by these students starts get motivated and involved in their interests according to certain topic. This has been totally assessed and widely accepted for teaching language in current world.

The previous systems for traditional communication were unfriendly to be sounded and unavailable for all languages using ordinary writing systems, whilst computer users communicate with programs using English. It seems to be that English teaching and learning become broaden via software programs and digitized artificial intellectual items. However, the days of not speaking other language restriction are over. There are some instances interface language and onscreen help now create new software more easily and rapidly customized for used languages. [8]

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